

Synthesis of Some New Mannich Bases of N-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzylidene)-4-methoxy benzoic acid hydrazide as Potential Biologically Active Agents

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A series of new Mannich bases from N-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy-benzylidene)-4-methoxy benzoic acid hydrazide has been synthesised and evaluated for their antibacterial and antiviral activities.

A large number of the hydrazides and hydrazones have been tested as antibacterial, antiviral and antitubercular agents¹⁻⁹. Besides, piperazine and other heterocyclic amino derivatives have been synthesised as biologically active agents⁹⁻¹⁰. In view of these observations, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise certain new Mannich bases from N-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy-benzylidene)-4-methoxy benzoic acid hydrazide(I). I was prepared according to the reported method¹¹ from 4-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide¹² and vanillin. I was then condensed with different secondary amines in the presence of formalin under Mannich conditions, to yield II, according to the scheme (1).

Mannich condensation with I could conceivably have given product with alternative structure IIIa but interpretation of nmr spectrum of the compound No.6 based on the following results confirms that only structure II was formed :

3.20 τ (singlet, 1H), 3.19 τ (doublet, J=9Hz, 2H), 2.87 τ (broad singlet, 1H), 1.97 τ (doublet, J=9Hz, 2H), 1.57 τ (broad singlet, 1H), -0.50 τ (broad singlet, exchangeable with D₂O, 1H), -1.16 τ (hump, exchangeable with D₂O, 1H).

Presence of three protons as singlets in the aromatic region together with two exchangeable protons in nmr spectrum of compound 6 completely rules out possibility of structure IIIa.

In case of compound 6 and 12 the stereochemistry of methyl group could not be definitely ascertained because of overlapping of nmr signals in the region 5.8-8.9 τ , it was difficult to analyse the splitting pattern of methine protons adjacent to the nitrogen of piperidine ring in the compound numbers 6 and 12.

All the synthesised compounds have adequately been characterised by correct elemental and infrared spectral studies.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are not corrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 G Spectrophotometer in KBr.

N-(4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxy-benzylidene)-4-methoxy-benzoic acid hydrazide(I) :

4-Methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide (1 mole) and vanillin (1 mole) were refluxed in ethanol with 3

drops of glacial acetic acid for 4 hr. The product obtained on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (pale yellow needles) m.p. 203° (lit⁹ 203-204°), yield 90%.

5-Substituted aminomethyl-N-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxy-benzylidene)-4-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazides(II) :

The hydrazone I (0.1 mole) was condensed with formaldehyde (0.15 mole) and secondary amine (0.1 mole) in ethanol by refluxing for 4 hr. Excess of the solvent was distilled off and product thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent. II, thus obtained are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—5-SUBSTITUTED AMINOMETHYL-N-(4'-HYDROXY-3'-METHOXY BENZYLIDENE)-4-METHOXY BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES(II)

Compound No.	Molecular formula	m.p.°C	%Nitrogen	
			Calculated	Found
1.	^c C ₂₂ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₄	211-212	10.50	10.50
2.	^c C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	205	10.50	10.00
3.	^b C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	190-91	10.96	10.80
4.	^a C ₂₇ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₄	224-25	11.81	11.32
5.	^a C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	217-18	13.59	13.25
6.	^a C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	188-189	10.24	10.30
7.	^b C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	138-140	11.60	11.46
8.	^b C ₂₇ H ₃₀ ClN ₂ O ₄	213-15	11.02	10.82
9.	^b C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	233-34	8.80	8.59
*10.	^d C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	208		
*11.	^d C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	218-19	11.47	11.09
*12.	^a C ₂₂ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₄	204-05		

+ % Analysis found C, 66.6% ; H, 7.35% ; requires C, 67.3% ; H, 6.8%.

* % Analysis found C, 66.6% ; H, 6.9% ; requires C, 67.3% ; H, 6.8%.

Compounds recrystallised from :
^a Ethanol
^b Methanol
^c Methanol/Propanol
^d Ethyl Acetate/Methanol

Yields of the compounds varied from 55-70%.

IR : 1. 3150(NH or OH), 2800-2900(CH₂), 1640(C=O), 1610(aryl).
 2. 3200(NH or OH), 2800(CH₂), 1640(C=O), 1600(aryl).
 3. 3130(NH or OH), 2800-2900(CH₂), 1638(C=O), 1600 (aryl).
 4. 3140(NH or OH), 2800(CH₂), 1640(C=O), 1600 (aryl).
 5. 3200(NH or OH), 2800(CH₂), 1640(C=O), 1604 (aryl).
 6. 3240(NH or OH), 2930(CH₂), 1640(C=O), 1604 (aryl).

Bio-Assay :

Antibacterial Activity : Six compounds (4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12) were tested against the strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Sarcina lutea* by

the reported agar diffusion method¹³. Compound No. 8 showed significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* ; others did not inhibit the growth of any strain.

Antiviral Activity : Six compounds (1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7) were tested against Tobacco mosaic virus. Compounds 1, 3 and 6 showed significant inhibition *in vivo*. Others were inactive.

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